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Review Article

Phytochemical and Pharmacological Insights into Helicteres Isora Linn: A Review of Its Properties

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ABSTRACT

The whole Plant of Helicteres Isora linn Showed excellent medicinal merits from ancient's time. The leaves, seeds, fruits, and roots of this plant have been used in ayurvedic medicines. It have give been refered for the treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery, abdominal colic pain, intestinal parasites. Helicteres Isora has Pharmacological actions like anti-oxidants, anticancer, antidiabetics, hypolipidemic, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotectives, brain oxidant potency, Anti diarrheal action, antispasmodic activity/ effect. In vivo method of animal testing is the use of nonhuman animals in experiments. Rats, Mice, rabbits, hamsters, guinea pigs and non-human primates are widely used as laboratory animals. Isolated chicken ileum is a better option available for conducting isolated tissue experiments considering the restriction with the use of experimental animals under CPCSEA guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Avaratani [helicteres Isora linn] is a medicinal plant which is used in several diseases. Helicteres Isora linn sometimes it's called as Indian screw tree and avartani, it is a small tree and it is found in the southern Asia and Northern Oceania. It is usually assigned in the family of malvaceae. Helicteres Isora linn it is used in ayurvedic, siddha, unani type of medicines¹.

Language	Name of plant
Marathi	Kewad, Murad Sheng
English	India Screw Tree
Hindi	Marorphala
Sanskrit	Avartani
Bengali	Atmora
Telugu	Guvadarra

Phytochemical Composition:

Phytochemical studies of the plant are crucial for identifying the bioactive compounds found in medicinal plants, which are essential for

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developing new drugs in the pharmaceutical industry. Screening of both the crude and methanol extracts reveals the presence of various compounds, including carbohydrates, saponins, tannins, proteins, steroids, anthraquinone glycosides, cardiac glycosides, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, alkaloid salts, and free

alkaloids. Additionally, the subcritical extract of the plant, prepared under conditions of 10 bar pressure, 160°C, a 1:30 sample to-solvent ratio, and a 30-minute extraction time, contains octadecenoic acid, hexadecanoic acid, and berberine².

Phytochemical screening of the Helicteres Isora linn. Fruit

Sr. No	Phytochemicals	Observation	Inference
1.	Carbohydrates	Red to violet ring at the junction of two liquids in Molisch's t	+
2.	Proteins	White precipitate obtained in xanthoprotein test	+
3.	Alkaloids	Cream-colored precipitate obtained with Mayer's reagent	+
4.	Cardiac glycosides	Yellow, orange to deep red colour obtained with Baljit reagent	+
5.	Flavonoids	Deep blue colour observed	+
6.	Tannins	Blue-green colour obtained with ferric chloride	+
7.	Essential oils	Red colour obtained in Sudan Red III test	+

Pharmacological Activity:

1. Antispasmodic Activity: -

The Antispasmodic Effect Is Believed to Be Due to The Inhibition of Acetylcholine-Induced Contractions. Acetylcholine Is a Neurotransmitter That Plays a Role in Muscle Contractions. By Inhibiting Its Action, Helicteres Isora Helps in Reducing Muscle Spasms⁴.

2. Anti-Diarrheal Activity: -

The Fruits, Which Have Astringent and Demulcent Properties⁵, Help Children With Flatulence and Bowel Cramping. For Diarrhea and Dysentery, The Bark Is Beneficial⁶

3. Antioxidant Activity: -

To Improve Safe Drug Delivery System Antioxidant Is a good Choice In deep Research. It Has Been Observed That Methanolic and Aqueous Extracts from The Fruits And Bark of Helicteres Isora Exhibit Antioxidant Activity, Including The Ability To Scavenge Free Radicals, Toxicity Towards Tumour Cells, And Protection Against Normal Cells⁷.

4. Anti-Diabetic: -

Activities The Root Extract of Helicteres Isora Has Been Shown To Have Insulin Sensitizing, Anti-

Hyperglycaemic, And Hypolipidemic Properties in Cumulative Research, Indicating That The Extract May Be Useful in The Treatment of Type 2 Diabetes. Experimental Research, Administering Rats with Diabetes Aqueous Bark Extract Significantly Reduced The Amount Of lipid Peroxidation Products While Also restoring the Heart's Natural Level⁸.

5. Anticancer Activity: -

According To pharmacology, The Medication Exhibits a Strong Anti-human Breast Cancer Effect. Alkaloids And Flavonoids Are the Source of The Drug's Cytotoxic Action. It Must Distinguish Between These Active Principles, Assess Them, And Clarify the Precise Mechanism of Action⁹.

6. Antimicrobial Activity:

Helicteres Isora Fruits, both methanolic And Aqueous, Have Been Shown By Some Researchers To Exhibit Antibacterial Efficacy Against a Variety of Bacterial Species. Antimicrobial Properties. Many Bacterial Strains' Antibiotic-Resistant Plasmid Can Be Removed By the Fruit's Acetone Extract, increasing The Strains' Sensitivity To Low Antibiotic Dosages. The Cured Derivatives' Numerous Antibiotic Resistances Were Reversed by Such plasmid Loss¹⁰.

7. Hypolepidemic activity:

The hypolipidemic properties of Helicteres Isora Linn. (Sterculiaceae) root extracts were examined in alloxan-induced diabetic rats, along with an exploration of the potential mechanism behind its blood glucose-lowering effects. Additionally, the impact of H. Isora bark extracts on serum lipoproteins, including high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), was analysed. Treatment with the bark extract of H. Isora resulted in a significant reduction of these lipoproteins, restoring them to near-normal levels in diabetic rats¹¹.

8. Antiplasmin activity:

Bioassay-guided isolation of active fractions with antiplasmin activity was performed from acetone extracts of shade-dried fruits of H. Isora. The active fraction facilitated plasmid curing, leading to the loss of antibiotic resistance encoded in the plasmids, as confirmed by the antibiotic resistance profiles of the cured strains. The physical elimination of plasmids was further verified through agarose gel electrophoresis¹².

9. Hepatoprotective activity:

Ethanollic root extracts of H. Isora have been shown to exhibit hepatoprotective effects against carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced liver damage in rats. The study assessed parameters such as serum total bilirubin, total protein, and the activities of alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase, and alkaline phosphatase. Biochemical analysis of blood samples from CCl₄-treated rats revealed a significant increase in serum markers and a decrease in total protein levels, indicating liver injury caused by CCl₄¹³.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, according to scientific research, the pharmacogenetic study of various parts of the plant is essential for authenticating drugs composed of numerous chemical constituents that have effects on the human body. Different parts of Helicteres Isora Linn exhibit distinct pharmacological activities. Studies evaluating antioxidant and anticancer properties using various solvent extracts (hexane, methanol, ethanol, and acetone) and crude protein have been conducted. The fruit has demonstrated antispasmodic activity, while both the fruits and roots have shown antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic effects, with flavonoids present in these parts contributing to these activities. Additionally, cytotoxic and antioxidant properties, linked to anticancer activities, have been identified through esteemed research efforts. Overall, it is evident that the entire plant has

significant medicinal value, warranting further investigations to isolate the active bioactive molecules responsible for treating various disorders.

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